

Studies on some less familiar Metal Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part XXII(a). Verification of Bhattacharya's Equation for Nickel, Manganese and Zinc Ferrocyanide Sols

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In an earlier communication¹ we had reported the results of our investigations on the colloidal properties of cobalt ferrocyanide. A few more new metal ferrocyanide sols have now been prepared and their coagulation studied with special reference to Bhattacharya's equation. The results of these investigations are reported in this communication.

Preparation of metal ferrocyanide sols.—The sols were prepared by the method of double decomposition. The amounts of metal salt and potassium ferrocyanide required to precipitate 2.5 gms. of the metal ferrocyanide were calculated from the following stoichiometric equations:

Calculated amounts of the reactants were mixed in the ratio of 1 equivalent of salt: 5.4 equivalents of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. The sol could only be obtained when the salt solution was gradually added to diluted $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution with constant stirring. Sols of the following maximum concentration could be obtained.

Nickel ferrocyanide sol=2.5 gms. per litre; manganese ferrocyanide sol=2.5 gms. per litre, zinc ferrocyanide sol=2.5 gms. per litre.

Time of slow coagulation: 5 cc. of each sol and varying amounts of electrolytes (KCl, HCl, BaCl_2 , AlCl_3) were taken in steam dried pyrex test tube and the total volume was made upto 10 cc. by the addition of doubly distilled water. The concentrations of the various electrolytes in the sols were so adjusted that the minimum time of coagulation was near about 30 min. in each case. Sols of concentration A, A/2 were used and the time at which the sol particles left the surface of the sol was taken as the time of coagulation.

From the precipitation concentration values it was inferred that the coagulating power for the various electrolytes is

The value of a , the critical stability concentration, in Bhattacharya's equation: $1/c - a = n/m \cdot t + 1/m$ was determined from the intercept on the concentration (c) axis from the plots of c and $1/t$ (inverse of time of coagulation). The constants m and n were determined from the straight lines obtained on plotting $1/c - a$ against t (Curves shown in Figs. 1 and 2). The values of the constants for the three sols are given in Table 1.

FIG. 1

TABLE I

Constants of Bhattacharya's equation for nickel, manganese and zincferrocyanide sols.

Electrolytes used.	Sols	Sol A			Sol A/2		
		a (mM/lit)	m (mM/lit.)	n^{-1} (minute)	a (mM/lit.)	m (mM/lit)	n^{-1} (minute)
M/2 KCl	Nickel ferrocyanide	40	200	80	34	333.3	124.8
	Mn. ferrocyanide	36	333	416.2	19.0	666.6	874.5
	Zinc "	87	660	775	65	166.0	157.7
M/200	Nickel "	0.64	0.31	0.31	0.36	1.25	1.25
BaCl ₂	Mn. "	0.28	5.00	4.5	0.14	10.00	12.8
	Zinc "	1.18	2.5	0.5	0.94	1.25	0.34
M/400	Nickel "	0.465	0.19	0.10	0.17	1.00	1.00
AlCl ₃	Mn. "	0.075	0.5	0.4	0.055	5.00	3.50
	Zinc "	0.365	2.0	0.4	0.21	0.38	0.28

From the Table 1 it is evident that the values of the empirical constants a , m and n decrease with increasing valency of the coagulating ions.

FIG. 2

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